

IMPLEMENTING THE PRINCIPLES OF QUALITY OF LIVING CONDITIONS IN MEDICAL SCIENCE

Nilufar Rasulova¹

Maftuna Sadikova²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

KEYWORDS

Quality of life, population health, public health, measuring quality of life, the impact of chronic diseases, prevention and early detection, access to medical care, social support, economic situation

ABSTRACT

The article examines the concept of quality of life, identifying its diverse impact on the physical, psychological, social and economic well-being of a person. Particular attention is paid to measuring quality of life and the impact of health on its various aspects. The authors of the article analyze the impact of chronic diseases on the quality of life, and also consider measures of prevention and early detection of diseases as key factors in increasing the duration and quality of life. The article covers in detail the organization of healthcare, socio-economic aspects of quality of life and the role of education in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

2181-2675/© 2024 in XALQARO TADQIQOT LLC.

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.14554878**

This is an open access article under the Attribution 4.0 International(CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

¹ Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

² Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

TIBBIYOT FANIDA HAYOT SIFATI SHARTLARI TAMOYILLARINI AMALIYOTGA TADBIQ QILIISH

KALIT SO‘ZLAR/ КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА:

Hayot sifati, aholi salomatligi, aholi salomatligi, hayot sifatini o'lchash, surunkali kasalliklarning ta'siri, oldini olish va erta aniqlash, tibbiy yordamdan foydalanish, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash, iqtisodiy vaziyat.

ANNOTATSIYA/ АННОТАЦИЯ

Maqolada hayot sifati tushunchasi ko'rib chiqiladi, uning insonning jismoniy, psixologik, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy farovonligiga turli xil ta'siri aniqlanadi. Hayot sifati va salomatlikning uning turli jihatlariga ta'sirini o'lchashga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Maqola mualliflari surunkali kasalliklarning hayot sifatiga ta'sirini tahlil qiladilar, shuningdek, kasalliklarning oldini olish va erta aniqlash choralari hayot davomiyligi va sifatini oshirishning asosiy omillari sifatida ko'rib chiqadilar. Maqolada sog'liqni saqlashni tashkil etish, hayot sifatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jihatlari va sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishda ta'limning roli batafsil yoritilgan.

Relevance. Additional attention is paid to measures to improve the quality of life through healthcare, including the development of primary health care and innovative approaches to treatment. Psychological support and countering stigma in health care are also seen as important components of providing a full level of care for the health of the population. The article concludes by emphasizing the need for an integrated public health approach to achieve a higher quality of life, and emphasizing the importance of innovation, education and social support in this process. This article provides a comprehensive overview of the factors influencing quality of life through the lens of health and suggests strategies for maximizing population well-being. Modern society faces many public health challenges, and one of the key aspects is the quality of life related to the health of the population. Studying this issue is of particular importance in the context of ensuring an effective health care system and improving public welfare. The definition of quality of life includes not only the absence of disease, but also the level of life satisfaction, access to medical care, social interactions and economic status. The multifaceted nature of this concept requires an integrated approach when measuring its various components. Health plays a key role in determining quality of life. Physical health affects activity and mobility, while psychological well-being determines emotional state. Measuring quality of life is important for determining the effectiveness of medical interventions, as well as for developing strategies to improve the living conditions of populations.

Health and its impact on quality of life. Health plays a key role in shaping a person's quality of life. Physical health influences activity and mobility, psychological well-being determines emotional well-being, and social interactions and economic status influence overall life satisfaction. Studying these relationships is becoming an important aspect of public health work. People suffering from chronic diseases often face restrictions in their

daily lives, which directly affects their quality of life. Public health must develop chronic disease management programs that focus not only on treatment but also on supporting patients to maintain an active and fulfilling lifestyle. The primary focus of public health should be on disease prevention. Prevention programs, promotion of healthy lifestyles and vaccinations contribute to improving the health of the population and, therefore, improving the quality of life. Prolonging active age and maintaining health in old age are becoming a public health priority. Organization of healthcare and quality of life. Ensuring access to medical care is becoming the main element influencing the quality of life of the population. Developing medical infrastructure, expanding the network of clinics and hospitals, and ensuring equal distribution of medical resources all contribute to improving the quality of healthcare and, as a result, improving the quality of life. Disease control and early detection play a key role in reducing morbidity and increasing life expectancy. Programs for regular medical examinations, screenings and public education help identify problems at an early stage and prevent the development of serious diseases. Socio-economic aspects of quality of life. Social support is important for quality of life. Social support is important for quality of life. Community programs aimed at supporting vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities, the elderly and low-income people, help improve their overall well-being and, consequently, their quality of life. Economic situation also greatly influences quality of life. Lack of stable income and social insurance can lead to limited access to health services. Community programs aimed at social and economic development can significantly improve the situation and reduce social inequalities in health care. Education and public awareness. Education plays a key role in creating a healthy lifestyle. Lack of stable income and social insurance can lead to limited access to health services. Community programs aimed at social and economic development can significantly improve the situation and reduce social inequalities in health care. Education and public awareness. Education plays a key role in creating a healthy lifestyle. Programs on healthy eating, physical activity and vaccinations should be introduced into the education system to increase public awareness. The role of health literacy. Health literacy of the population is becoming an important aspect of public health. The more informed people are about their health, the easier it is for them to make informed decisions about their lifestyle and treatment. Public health literacy campaigns can play a key role in this process. Measures to improve quality of life through healthcare. Primary health care is the foundation of healthcare and a key element in improving quality of life. Public health literacy campaigns can play a key role in this process. Measures to improve quality of life through healthcare. Primary health care is the foundation of healthcare and a key element in improving quality of life. The development of a network of clinics, provision of qualified doctors and availability of medicines at the primary level helps reduce the burden on specialized institutions and provides the population with the necessary medical care. The introduction of innovative methods of treatment and rehabilitation helps to increase the effectiveness of medical interventions and reduce the

recovery period. The use of technology, telemedicine and personalized treatments opens up new prospects for improving the quality of life of patients.

Psychological support and a stigma-free society Psychological support is becoming an integral part of the healthcare system. Providing access to mental health care and support for people with mental illness helps reduce stigma and ensures full participation in society. Stigma associated with certain diseases can be a barrier to getting help. Public campaigns and educational programs aim to counter stigma and promote an open and supportive society. In modern society, where public health is becoming a key aspect of well-being, the concept of quality of life takes center stage. Quality of life covers a wide range of factors, including physical, psychological, social and economic well-being. Public campaigns and educational programs aim to counter stigma and promote an open and supportive society. In modern society, where public health is becoming a key aspect of well-being, the concept of quality of life takes center stage. Quality of life covers a wide range of factors, including physical, psychological, social and economic well-being. Within public health, assessing and measuring quality of life is becoming an important tool for determining the effectiveness of health interventions and developing strategies to improve overall well-being. The definition of quality of life includes not only the absence of disease, but also the level of life satisfaction, access to medical care, social interactions and economic status. The multifaceted nature of this concept requires an integrated approach when measuring its various components. Health plays a key role in determining quality of life. Physical health affects activity and mobility, while psychological well-being determines emotional state. Social interactions and economic status also greatly influence overall life satisfaction. This interaction between health and quality of life is becoming an integral part of public health research. People suffering from chronic diseases often face limitations in their daily lives, which directly affects their quality of life. Disease prevention and early detection play an important role in improving public health and quality of life. Public health should emphasize disease prevention as well as the development of chronic disease management programs. Healthcare organization plays a key role in shaping the quality of life. Access to medical care is becoming a fundamental element that influences the level of health care. Developing medical infrastructure, expanding the network of clinics and hospitals, and ensuring equal distribution of medical resources all contribute to improving the quality of healthcare and improving public welfare. Preventive measures and early detection of diseases are important components of healthcare organization. Public health must develop chronic disease management programs that focus not only on treatment but also on supporting patients to maintain an active and fulfilling lifestyle. The primary focus of public health should be on disease prevention Prevention programs, promotion of healthy lifestyles and vaccinations contribute to improving the health of the population and, therefore, improving the quality of life. Prolonging active age and maintaining health in old age are becoming a public health priority. Regular medical examinations, screenings and educational programs

are aimed at identifying problems in the early stages and preventing the development of serious diseases. Social support is important for shaping quality of life. Programs aimed at supporting vulnerable groups, including the disabled, the elderly and the poor, improve their overall well-being and therefore their quality of life. Economic situation also greatly influences quality of life.

Conclusions. A comprehensive consideration of health-related quality of life in a public health context reveals the inherent link between health and social well-being. Effective healthcare management, medical innovation, emphasis on prevention and early detection, social support and anti-stigma are key strategies for improving quality of life. Public health plays a critical role in this process by ensuring access to health care and creating the conditions for a full, healthy and satisfying life for everyone in society. Health-related quality of life is a complex and interrelated issue that requires a comprehensive public health approach. Health-related quality of life is a complex and interrelated issue that requires a comprehensive public health approach. Introduction of innovative methods, development of the primary health care system, social support.

Literature used

1. Kulikov, S. I. (2011). Pedagogical foundations of the professional activity of a modern doctor. Abstract of thesis... cand. pedagogical Sci. Kaliningrad, 8.
2. Zavyalov, A. E. (2013). Formation of a healthy lifestyle of young people in modern Russia. Author's abstract. diss....cand. sociol. Sci.
3. Andronnikova, O. O., & Veterok, E. V. (2016). Psychological well-being and health as an urgent need of a modern person in the framework of victimization. *Bulletin of Kemerovo State University*, (1 (65)), 72-76.
4. Petrash, M. D., & Murtazina, I. R. (2018). The concept of "healthy lifestyle" in psychological research. *Bulletin of St. Petersburg University. Psychology*, 8(2), 152-165.
5. Lebedeva, A. A. // Subjective well-being of persons with disabilities. Moscow. 2020
6. Давлетьянц, Г. Л., Нуритдинова, Н. Б., Зуева, Е. Б., & Усманов, Р. И. (2000). Клиническая и гемодинамическая эффективность небиволола у больных с гипертонической болезнью и сердечной недостаточностью. *Кардиология*, 40(12), 64.
7. Абдуллаев, С. П., Бендингер, М. Н., Юлдашева, Х. Ю., Нуритдинова, Н. Б., & Шукурджанова, С. М. (2010). Особенности лечения артериальной гипертензии у лиц пожилого возраста. *Кардиология Узбекистана. Ташкент*, (2-3), 17.
8. Ярмухамедова, Д. З., Нуритдинова, Н. Б., Шоалимова, З. М., Махмудова, М. С., & Ибрагимов, З. С. (2021). РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОСТЬ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИИ И ФАКТОРОВ РИСКА У ЛИЦ МОЛОДОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *Наука, техника и образование*, (3 (78)), 60-63.
9. Mahmudova, M. S., Shukurdjanova, S. M., & Nuritdinova, N. B. (2022). Complications of Parkes Weber syndrome.

10. Абдумаликова, Ф. Б., Нуриллаева, Н. М., Нуритдинова, Н. Б., & Шукурджанова, С. М. (2021). Влияние пандемии COVID-19 на поведенческие и психосоциальные факторы риска сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний.
11. Sobirova, D. R., Azizova, F. X., Ishandjanova, S. X., Otajanova, A. N., & Uterova, N. B. (2021). Study of changes in pulmonary alveolar epithelium and aerogemetic barrier in diabetes mellitus.
12. Собирова, Д. Р., Нуралиев, Н. А., & Усманов, Р. Д. (2018). Оценка медико-биологической безопасности генно-модифицированного продукта. *Методические рекомендации*, 19, 38-40.
13. Sobirova, D. R., & Shamansurova, K. S. (2016). Features of influence of the new product obtained by new technologies on animal organism in the experiment. In *The Eleventh European Conference on Biology and Medical Sciences* (pp. 44-46).
14. Собирова, Д. Р., Усманов, Р. Д., Азизова, Ф. Х., Шигакова, Л. А., & Утепова, Н. Б. (2023, June). ҚАНДЛИ ДИАБЕТ КАСАЛЛИГИДА ЎПКАНИНГ МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ. In *Conferences* (pp. 40-41).
15. Палванова, У., Якубова, А., & Юсупова, Ш. (2023). УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРИ СПЕНОМЕГАЛИИ. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(21).
16. Якубова, А. Б., & Палванова, У. Б. Проблемы здоровья связанные с экологией среди населения Приаралья мақола Научно-медицинский журнал "Авиценна" Выпуск № 13. Кемерово 2017г, 12-15.
17. Азада, Б. Я., & Умида, Б. П. (2017). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЗДОРОВЬЯ СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ЭКОЛОГИЕЙ СРЕДИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ПРАРАЛЬЯ. *Авиценна*, (13), 12-14.
18. Степанян, И. А., Изранов, В. А., Гордова, В. С., Белецкая, М. А., & Палванова, У. Б. (2021). Ультразвуковое исследование печени: поиск наиболее воспроизводимой и удобной в применении методики измерения косоугольного размера правой доли. *Лучевая диагностика и терапия*, 11(4), 68-79.
19. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., Beleckaya, M. A., & Palvanova, U. B. (2021). Ultrasound examination of the liver: the search for the most reproducible and easy to operate measuring method of the right lobe oblique craniocaudal diameter. *Diagnostic radiology and radiotherapy*, 11(4), 68-79.
20. Batirovna, Y. A., Bahramovna, P. U., Bahramovna, P. S., & Ogli, I. A. U. (2019). Effective treatment of patients with chronic hepatitis, who live in ecologically unfavorable South zone of Aral Sea region. *Наука, образование и культура*, (2 (36)), 50-52.